

Dendrochronological analysis of additional timbers from a shipwreck at Skeppsholmen, Stockholm.

by

Aoife Daly.

Dendro.dk report 5 : 2018

Commissioned by Jim Hansson, Swedish National Maritime Museums.

Six samples from Skeppsholmen, Stockholm, were submitted for dendrochronological analysis, to determine their date and provenance. Twelve ship timbers have been analysed previously from the site showing that the oaks for the ship were felled in the years 1612-13 and 1613-14 (Daly 2017). Five of the additional samples are from the aft of the ship and include oak hull planks, an oak ceiling and pine sheathing. A sixth sample is from a separate structure. The results of this analysis are described in this report.

Skeppsholmen, Stockholm

The ship timbers

Of the five additional samples from the ship three are of *Quercus sp.*, oak while the remaining two are *Pinus sp.*, pine. Two of the oaks and both pine samples are dated.

The oak samples

Two oak samples (p5 & p4) are from hull planks, tangentially converted from the parent tree. Both these samples could be dated. Plank p5 had 10 sapwood years preserved. Allowing for missing sapwood, the tree used for making this plank is calculated to have been felled in AD 1606-20. The sample from plank p4 has 12 sapwood rings preserved. It is from a tree felled in AD 1611-23. The dating of these two hull planks agrees with the dating of the other oak material, previously analysed from the ship (see fig. 1).

A third oak sample is from a ceiling plank. It contains 141 tree-rings, but displays severe growth distortion. The sample might have been taken at a knotty part of the plank. The tree-ring curve could not be dated.

The pine samples

The two pine samples are from sheathing, applied to the outer hull. Both these samples are dated. No bark edge is observed on these two samples. Sample p2 contains 172 tree-rings and is from a tree felled after AD 1604. Sample p3 contains 253 tree-rings. This plank is from a tree felled after AD 1623.

It seems clear that the pine outer sheathing was a feature added some ten years or so after the ship was built.

Fig. 1. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. The chronological position of the dated samples. Green are oak and the orange are pine.

			Z207003a	Z2070019	Z207009a	Z207007a	Z207002a	Z2070169	Z207008a	Z207011a	Z207004a	Z2070129	Z207006a	Z2070149	Z2070159
Average Z207M004	P1	Z207003a	*	4,00	1,18	2,82	1,22	1,18	2,37	2,8	3,21	1,27	2,19	1,89	1,55
	P21	Z2070019	4,00	*	5,38	5,44	2,04	4,65	3,98	3,19	3,51	4,25	2,48	1,67	-
	P22	Z207009a	1,18	5,38	*	3,10	1,35	1,6	2,48	1,28	3,47	5,21	1,2	1,56	-
	P20	Z207007a	2,82	5,44	3,10	*	5,05	5,37	3,84	2,19	1,47	3,39	-	2,57	-
	P9	Z207002a	1,22	2,04	1,35	5,05	*	4,85	2,56	2,61	1,44	2,97	3,52	-	-
	NewP4	Z2070169	1,18	4,65	1,6	5,37	4,85	*	5,36	4,04	2,54	4,21	2,25	-	-
	P10	Z207008a	2,37	3,98	2,48	3,84	2,56	5,36	*	4,77	3,85	3,71	4,70	2,02	-
	P8	Z207011a	2,8	3,19	1,28	2,19	2,61	4,04	4,77	*	5,29	4,46	4,50	1,62	-
	P17	Z207004a	3,21	3,51	3,47	1,47	1,44	2,54	3,85	5,29	*	7,40	3,61	1,84	-
	NewP5	Z2070129	1,27	4,25	5,21	3,39	2,97	4,21	3,71	4,46	7,40	*	3,10	2,21	-
	P7	Z207006a	2,19	2,48	1,2	-	3,52	2,25	4,70	4,50	3,61	3,10	*	-	-
Ave Z207M003	NewP3	Z2070149	1,89	1,67	1,56	2,57	-	-	2,02	1,62	1,84	2,21	-	*	5,05
	NewP2	Z2070159	1,55	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	5,05	*

Table 1. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation (t -value) between the tree-ring curves from each of the dated samples from the ship with each other. The grey tone highlights the high t -values. Green are oak (the two new samples are shown in light green) and the orange are pine.

Provenance

In table 1 the correlation (t -value) of the dated tree-ring curves from the ship with each other is shown. The two oaks analysed here are cross-matching with the previous material from the ship. A new average (Z207M004) is made, from all the dated oaks from the ship. It is 201 years in length and covers the period AD 1413-1613.

The correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets for oak for Northern Europe is shown in table 2. The oak from the Skeppsholmen ship is achieving highest correlation (t -values) with material from the Vasa ship, currently under analysis, in the research project TIMBER (ERC project no. 677152) based at Copenhagen University. It is emerging that the timbers from Vasa are forming several groups, and the groups that the Skeppsholmen ship's oaks are dating with are probably from Småland.

An average (Z207M003) of the tree-ring curves from the two pine samples is also made. This average is 253 years long, covering the period AD 1369-1621. The correlation between this average and a range of tree-ring datasets for pine for Northern Europe is shown in table 3. The pine is achieving the highest correlation with chronologies from the Stockholm and Uppland regions of Sweden. The timber for the sheathing might have grown in the Stockholm hinterland.

Filename	-	-	Ship all Z207M004	
-	start	dates	AD 1413	
-	dates	end	AD 1613	
Site chronologies				
Z0921M02	AD 1424	AD 1609	10.19	Vasa hull planks mostly 11 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z0922M01	AD 1404	AD 1622	7.52	Vasa group 1 35 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z0922M02	AD 1330	AD 1625	6.09	Vasa group 2 37 timbers [Daly in prep]
Z109M001	AD 1437	AD 1597	5.83	Barcode ship 1 BC01 Oslo 4 timbers [Daly 2013]
6094M002	AD 1450	AD 1660	5.66	Funder kirke later material 4 timbers [Daly 2002]
Single trees				
Z092101b	AD 1424	AD 1607	7.06	Vasa ship bitt midships aft upper canon deck [Daly in prep]
Z092114a	AD 1357	AD 1612	7.06	Vasa frame at GP9 D37 lower gundeck sb [Daly in prep]
Z092118a	AD 1452	AD 1568	6.95	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D16 [Daly in prep]
Z0921179	AD 1470	AD 1593	6.82	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D15 [Daly in prep]
Z092150a	AD 1436	AD 1608	6.81	Vasa D51 ceiling right side GP4 ÖB ps [Daly in prep]
Z092117b	AD 1470	AD 1593	6.80	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D15 [Daly in prep]
BAT6047a	AD 1426	AD 1586	6.56	Batavia Western Australia 6047 frame [Daly 2016]
Z092236a	AD 1502	AD 1625	6.41	Vasa D137 frame GP16 NB ps [Daly in prep]
Z092148a	AD 1509	AD 1622	6.36	Vasa D49 frame GP4 ÖB ps [Daly in prep]
Z092120a	AD 1477	AD 1607	6.12	Vasa D18 ceiling plank GP12 top left [Daly in prep]
Z092117a	AD 1473	AD 1593	6.00	Vasa outer hull plank GP20 D15 upper right [Daly in prep]
Z092111a	AD 1440	AD 1593	5.94	Vasa outer plank GP24 D13 upper gundeck [Daly in prep]
Z092198a	AD 1454	AD 1588	5.70	Vasa D99 sill GP1 ÖB sb [Daly in prep]
Z092241a	AD 1433	AD 1614	5.69	Vasa D142 frame GP20 NB ps [Daly in prep]

Table 2. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the oak average curve for the ship and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Stone box

The sixth sample analysed here is from the framing for a stone-filled box (*stenkista*). This sample is *Pinus sp.*, pine and contains 152 tree-rings.

Unfortunately this sample could not be dated.

Methodology

Measuring and analysis of the material is carried out using the program "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and for the calculation of the t -value ("t-test") "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) is used. To estimate the felling dates of the oak trees a sapwood average of c. 10-25 sapwood rings is used. Several calculations of the average sapwood in oaks in different regions in Northern Europe have been published, and as the provenance of the oaks used to build the ship at Skeppsholmen is likely to be Småland, I have here chosen to use a combination of the estimate for Northern Germany (ca. 20 sapwood years (-5+10) (Hollstein 1980)) and for Northern Poland (15 years (-6 +9) (Wazny 1990)). There is no published sapwood statistic for Sweden, as far as I am aware.

In pine and spruce using the number of sapwood rings to estimate the felling date in the absence of bark edge is highly problematical, due to the wide variation in the number of sapwood rings. It can also be difficult to identify the sapwood edge in waterlogged archaeological conifer timbers. Sapwood has therefore not been recorded in this analysis, and felling, in the absence of bark edge, is placed at after the date of the outermost preserved tree-ring.

In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are consulted.

Filenames	-	-	Z2070149	Z2070159	Z207M003	
-	start	dates	AD 1369	AD 1431	AD 1369	
-	dates	end	AD 1621	AD 1602	AD 1621	
SWED_STK	AD 1127	AD 1671	9.75	5.27	8.97	Stockholm/Uppland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_UP1	AD 1031	AD 1638	8.15	6.59	8.81	Uppland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_HL1	AD 1001	AD 1861	5.96	5.09	6.31	Helsingland [Bartholin pers comm]
30530010	AD 1343	AD 1669	7.82	3.99	6.24	Skeppsholmen Stockholm 36 series [Eggertsson pers comm]
gaepin01	AD 1212	AD 1883	6.95	4.53	6.02	Gaestrikland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_DAL	AD 1001	AD 1852	5.59	3.23	5.28	Dalarna [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_AAL	AD 1068	AD 1827	5.21	-	5.25	Aaland [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED_GOT	AD 1124	AD 1987	6.03	-	5.14	Gotland [Bartholin pers comm]
Danson1	AD 1489	AD 1758	3.35	4.03	5.08	Danson House Bexley Kent [C Tyers pers comm]
FYRSVEN3	AD 1353	AD 1636	5.28	-	5.04	Svendborg pine [Bartholin pers comm]
SWED022	AD 1127	AD 1987	5.90	-	4.58	Gotland [Fritz Schweingruber]
JM11627t	AD 1368	AD 1587	4.99	-	4.10	London Westminster 107 Jermyn Street [C Tyers pers comm]
SWED_GRV	AD 1469	AD 1840	6.06	-	3.46	Gravsten [Bartholin pers comm]

Table 3. Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. Result of the correlation between the two curves for pine sheathing and diverse site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

Literature

- Baillie, M.G.L. and Pilcher, J.R., 1973. A simple crossdating program for tree-ring research. *Tree-Ring Bulletin* 33, 7-14.
- Daly, A., 2002. Dendrokronologisk undersøgelse af tømmer fra Funder kirke, Århus amt. *Nationalmuseets Naturvidenskabelige Undersøgelser rapport nr. 2002:19*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2013. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from three ships - BC01, BC03 & BC10, from Barcode, Oslo. *Dendro.dk report 2013:33*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2016. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from Batavia, a Dutch ship, wrecked off the Australian coast. *Dendro.dk report 2016:58*, Copenhagen.
- Daly, A., 2017. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from a shipwreck and waterfront at Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. *Dendro.dk report 2017:54*, Copenhagen.
- Hollstein, E. 1980. *Mitteleuropäische Eichenchronologie*. Trierer Grabungen und Forschungen 11. Mainz am Rhein.
- Tyers, I.G., 1997. Dendro for Windows Program Guide, *ARCUS Report 340*, Sheffield.
- Wazny, T., 1990. *Aufbau und Anwendung der Dendrochronologie für Eichenholz in Polen*. PhD Thesis. Universität Hamburg, pp. 213.

Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number, species	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Ship											
Z2070129	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p5 Brobanken QUSP	134	AD 1472	AD 1605	F	10	N	T	S1	1,07	AD 1606-20
Z2070149	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p3 Forhudring Brobanken PISY	253	AD 1369	AD 1621	F	0	N	T	H1	0,68	after AD 1623
Z2070159	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p2 Forhudring Aktem PISY	172	AD 1431	AD 1602	F	0	N	T	H1	1,11	after AD 1604
Z2070169	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p4 Bordlaggning Akter QUSP	130	AD 1481	AD 1610	G	12	N	T	S1	0,92	AD 1611-23
Z2070179	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p1 innergarnering QUSP	141			F	0	N	O	H1	1,68	undated
Stenkiste											
Z2070139	Stockholm Skeppsholmen p6 Plank båd/Stenkista PISY	152			G	0	?	T	N	0,91	undated
Averages											
Z207M003	Stockholm Skeppsholmen Forhudring 2 timbers PISY	253	AD 1369	AD 1621						0,84	
Z207M004	Stockholm Skeppsholmen wreck 11 timbers QUSP	201	AD 1413	AD 1613						1,46	
Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion. Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 - 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings. QUSP = <i>Quercus sp.</i> , oak. PISY = <i>Pinus sp.</i> , pine. PCAB = <i>Picea sp/Larix sp.</i> , spruce/larch											
Aoife Daly, Ph.D.			1st February 2018								

When quoting these results please add the following: in publication bibliography/literature lists:

Daly, Aoife, 2018. Dendrochronological analysis of additional timbers from a shipwreck at Skeppsholmen, Stockholm. *dendro.dk report 2018:5*, Copenhagen.

In blogs and social media: *dendro.dk report 2018:5*